

DTU Edible

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INTRODUCTION

To create a sustainable future, one first has to create a sustainable mindset. And as with many technical and environmental efforts to reduce our consumption of goods and energy, a solution is only efficient when followed by a subsequent change of mentality amongst the users.

The idea is here to directly change the mentality amongst the users by forcing an attack on their alienation from nature. This is achieved by making them all first-hand direct users of the actual nature on DTU campus, switching over to planting a purely edible greenery selection and basically transforming DTU into an edible campus.

OVERVIEW

Human learning is always strong when we are given visualizations, and even further intensified more when we are given pure hands-on experience. Most of the greatest inventions and design revolutions of mankind have always been coupled with a rigid observation and understanding of nature.

As a campus on a huge area with a living green environment, this area could itself be put to use to create a more intimate atmosphere between all the users of DTU and the campus itself.

The project would be to analyze the total area and map it for potential replacements in the current planting with an all-edible selection of trees, shrubberies, flowers and roots. Furthermore the project should include a cost- and effort-analysis.

CONCLUSION

As students native to agricultural backgrounds, we have found the complete agricultural and forage-related illiteracy as shocking as it is ominous.

Society as a whole needs to think outside the box in its ways to make students and inhabitants feel as a partaking element of a sustainable future, and by completing such a transition to an edible campus DTU will put itself foremost as being an innovative university working towards sustainability.